

Study on the Evaluation of the Chaotic Cipher System Using the Improved Volterra Filters and the RBFN Mapping

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose a chaotic cipher system consisting of Improved Volterra Filters and the mapping that is created from the actual voice by using Radial Basis Function Network. In order to achieve a practical system, the system supposes to use the digital communication line, such as the Internet, to maintain the parameter matching between the transmitter and receiver sides. Therefore, in order to withstand the attack from outside, it is necessary that complicate the internal state and improve the sensitivity coefficient. In this paper, we validate the robustness of proposed method from three perspectives of “Chaotic properties”, “Randomness”, “Coefficient sensitivity”.

Keywords—Chaos cipher, 16-bit-length fixed-point arithmetic, Volterra filter, Secret communications, RBF Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

RECENTLY, digital communication network such as the Internet has evolved significantly. As a result, the demand for secret communication is increasing. And, the chaotic cipher is a very effective means in the realization of secret communication [1]. The reason for it is based on the characteristics of the chaos: (1) the Sensitive Dependence on Initial Conditions, (2) Orbital Instability, (3) Long-term Unpredictability. By these properties, the correct transfer of information becomes possible only if an initial value and parameters are fully compatible between the sender and receiver.

We have studied and proposed the chaotic cipher using chaotic neuron and linear/nonlinear digital filters [2]. When the modem system using the proposed cipher is realized, the limited bit-length arithmetic with fixed decimal point is used in our study [3] [4] [5]. However, the signal generated by the finite bit length operation will become pseudo-chaos, characteristics of the chaos is lowered. It is impossible to avoid that the generated signal becomes pseudo chaos; therefore, it is necessary to improve sensitive to the parameter mismatch by other approaches.

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In this paper, we examine to incorporate the nonlinear filters called Volterra Filter into the chaotic cipher system. Moreover, by using the Radial Basis Function Network (RBF Network) for pattern classification and function approximation problems, we aim to synthesize fluctuations of vocal cords from real voice and create a robust mapping [6]. Then, the system using these methods is proposed and the robustness is evaluated.

II. PROPERTY OF THE FIXED-POINT ARITHMETIC

Fig. 1 Flow of the 16 bit-length Fixed-Point Arithmetic

In this study, the chaotic cipher system is assuming the use of 16 bit-length fixed-point arithmetic that used in the Digital Signal Processor. Fig. 1 shows the flow of the 16 bit length fixed-point arithmetic. In the figure, the decimal point is assumed to the tenth bit by the least significant bit. In this research, we call this format “Q₁₀ Format”.

When the Q₁₀ Format is used, the overflow may occur during addition and subtraction. Moreover, when multiplication is carried out, because a calculation result is expressed in 32 bit-length data once, both the round-off and the overflow occur by the process that converts the result into 16 bit-length data. By the features on such calculations, the units of the Q₁₀ format (Q_{10unit}), minimum value (Q_{10min}), maximum value (Q_{10max}) is as follows.

$$Q_{10unit} = 2^{-10} \cong 0.000977 \quad (1)$$

$$Q_{10min} = -2^{16-10-1} \cong -32.000000 \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{10max} = 2^{16-10-1} - Q_{10unit} = 31.999023 \quad (3)$$

In other words, the variables using the Q_{10} format can be operated in this limited range. This feature is effective, so any unstable linear and nonlinear digital filters can be realized with the boundedness by the overflow that occurs during operation. In this study, the feature of the Q_{10} Format has been used for the boundedness property that is required for chaos can be realized.

III. MAPPING OF RBF NETWORK

A. Fluctuation of Vocal Cords

At first glance, Speech waveform of the real voice seems to have a periodic structure. However, the shape of the waveform has been a slight change in every cycle, and that has been changed subtly in width of period accordingly. The difference in width of the period is called “fluctuation of vocal cords”.

Fig. 2 The Fluctuation of Vocal Cords

B. RBF Network

RBF Network is a kind of deformed three-layer network, and by overlaying the localized basis functions called radial basis function, it has been considered as the way to complement any function as intended.

The formula that represents the structure of RBF Network that obtains one dimensional output $f(x)$ to k dimensional inputs is shown in (4).

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^M \omega_i \varphi_i(r) \quad (4)$$

Here, $\varphi_i(r)$ is the basis function, ω_i is the coupling coefficient of it, M is the amount of it. Then, the basis function $\varphi_i(r)$ is using the Gaussian function as follows (5) and Fig. 3.

$$\varphi_i(r) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x_k - \mu_i\|}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

In addition, we have given 3 dimensional that is number of internal state variables in chaotic cipher to k . Here, x_k is input vector, and σ is variance. μ_i is center vector of the i -th, and it is determined depending on the number of radial basis function. And, the interior of “ $\| \|$ ” shows the Euclidean norm. The weights ω_i can be obtained by using the least squares method. Result of RBF Network is vary greatly by the value of these center vectors and M .

The structure of the RBF Network is shown in Fig. 4. In this study, we call this mapping “RBFN Mapping”.

Fig. 3 Gaussian Function of RBF

Fig. 4 The Structure of RBF Network

IV. CHAOTIC CIPHER SYSTEM

Expressions of the conventional method that had been proposed in our study are shown below:

$$x_1(n) = s(n) - G(x_1(n-1)) + g_1 \cdot x_3(n-1) + \theta_1, \quad (6)$$

$$x_2(n) = \theta_2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 h_i \cdot x_i(n-1) + h_{123} \cdot \prod_{i=1}^3 x_i(n-1) + \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 h_{ij} \cdot x_i(n-1) \cdot x_j(n-1), \quad (7)$$

$$x_3(n) = x_2(n-1). \quad (8)$$

The conventional system is constructed by the chaotic neuron type nonlinearity ((6)) and the 2nd order Volterra Filter ((7)).

$$r(n) = x_1(n) + G(x_1(n-1)) - g_1 \cdot x_3(n-1) - \theta_1, \quad (9)$$

$$x_2(n) = \theta_2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 h_i \cdot x_i(n-1) + h_{123} \cdot \prod_{i=1}^3 x_i(n-1) + \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 h_{ij} \cdot x_i(n-1) \cdot x_j(n-1), \quad (10)$$

$$x_3(n) = x_2(n-1). \quad (11)$$

The function $G(x)$ is a discontinuous function: the property of the discontinuous function becomes a parameter key on the cipher. The function $G(x)$ is set to below:

$$G(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{(Min - Max) \cdot x + (Max - a_1) \cdot Min}{Min - a_1} & : Min \leq x \leq a_1 \\ \frac{(Max - Min) \cdot x + (a_1 \cdot Min - a_2 \cdot Max)}{a_1 - a_2} & : a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ \frac{(Min - Max) \cdot x + (a_2 \cdot Max - a_3 \cdot Min)}{a_2 - a_3} & : a_2 \leq x \leq a_3 \\ \frac{(Max - Min) \cdot x + (a_3 \cdot Min - Max^2)}{a_3 - Max} & : a_3 \leq x \leq Max \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

If all parameters $\theta_1, \theta_2, g_1, h_i, h_{ij}, h_{123}$ and the initial value of internal state variables $x_1(0), x_2(0), x_3(0)$ on the transmitter and the receiver sides accord perfectly, the volterra filters of both transmitter and receiver synchronizes, as the results, the information signal $s(n)$ is completely demodulated as $r(n)$. Besides, (6) ~ (12) are originally designed so that it is carried out by the fixed-point arithmetic because the system does not have boundness. Namely, the boundness that is required as a chaotic map is given by the fixed-point arithmetic.

Expressions of the transmitter side in the proposed system that are proposed in this study are shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(n) &= s(n) + \theta_1 \\ &+ RBFN(x_1(n-1), x_2(n-1), x_3(n-1)) \\ &+ (g_{22} \cdot x_2(n-1)^2 + g_{33} \cdot x_3(n-1)) \\ &+ g_{123} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1) \cdot x_3(n-1), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} x_2(n) &= \theta_2 + (h_1 x_1(n-1) + h_3 x_3(n-1)) \\ &+ (h_{12} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1)) \\ &+ h_{13} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_3(n-1) \\ &+ h_{23} \cdot x_2(n-1) \cdot x_3(n-1) \\ &+ h_{31} \cdot x_3(n-1) \cdot x_1(n-1) \\ &+ h_{32} \cdot x_3(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1) \\ &+ h_{123} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1) \cdot x_3(n-1), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} x_3(n) &= x_2(n-1) + (g_1 x_1(n-1) + g_3 x_3(n-1)) \\ &+ (g_{12} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1)) \\ &+ g_{21} \cdot x_2(n-1) \cdot x_1(n-1) \\ &+ g_{31} \cdot x_3(n-1) \cdot x_1(n-1) \\ &+ g_{32} \cdot x_3(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Expressions of the receiver side in the proposed system that are proposed in this study are shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(n) &= s(n) - \theta_1 \\ &- RBFN(x_1(n-1), x_2(n-1), x_3(n-1)) \\ &- (g_{22} \cdot x_2(n-1)^2 + g_{33} \cdot x_3(n-1)) \\ &- g_{123} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1) \cdot x_3(n-1), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} x_2(n) &= \theta_2 + (h_1 x_1(n-1) + h_3 x_3(n-1)) \\ &+ (h_{12} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1)) \\ &+ h_{13} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_3(n-1) \\ &+ h_{23} \cdot x_2(n-1) \cdot x_3(n-1) \\ &+ h_{31} \cdot x_3(n-1) \cdot x_1(n-1) \\ &+ h_{32} \cdot x_3(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1) \\ &+ h_{123} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1) \cdot x_3(n-1), \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} x_3(n) &= x_2(n-1) + (g_1 x_1(n-1) + g_3 x_3(n-1)) \\ &+ (g_{12} \cdot x_1(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1)) \\ &+ g_{21} \cdot x_2(n-1) \cdot x_1(n-1) \\ &+ g_{31} \cdot x_3(n-1) \cdot x_1(n-1) \\ &+ g_{32} \cdot x_3(n-1) \cdot x_2(n-1). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

The proposed system is constructed by the RBFN Mapping ((13)) and the two Volterra Filters ((14), (15)). But, the two Volterra Filters are has been modified as follows: some parameters ($\theta_1, h_{11}, h_{22}, h_{33}, h_{123}$) in the third formula have been transposed to the first formula, some parameter that don't have a significant impact at the sophisticate of encryption have been erased. The reason for this modification is as follows: Improvement of properties that are sensitive to parameter mismatch, the optimization of encryption processing. In this study, we call this filter "Improved Volterra Filters".

In addition, as with the conventional method, if all parameters $\theta_1, \theta_2, g_i, g_{ij}, g_{123}, h_i, h_{ij}, h_{123}$ and the initial value of internal state variables $x_1(0), x_2(0), x_3(0)$ on the transmitter and the receiver sides accord perfectly, as the results, the information signal $s(n)$ is completely demodulated as $r(n)$.

V. EVALUATION OF THE EACH SYSTEMS

In this chapter, we evaluate property of the conventional and proposed systems. The each system is evaluated by three types items: in the chaotic property, randomness, the sensitivity coefficient. In each evaluation, the initial value of internal state variables are 0.0, and the value of the unchanging parameters is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} g_i &= g_{ij} = g_{123} = h_i = h_{ij} = h_{123} = 1.0, \\ \alpha &= 1.0, \theta_1 = \theta_2 = 0.1, \\ Min &= 0X0000, Max = 0XFFFF, \\ a_1 &= -16.0, a_2 = 0.0, a_3 = 16.0. \end{aligned}$$

The parameters of RBF Network are as follows:
 $\sigma = 48.0, M = 10$.

A. Chaotic Property

In this subsection, we try to evaluate the chaotic property of the proposed cipher based on the Lyapunov exponents [7]. The Lyapunov exponent is one of the quantitative indexes of chaos.

If the maximum Lyapunov exponent is a positive number, the system can be categorized into chaotic.

When the Lyapunov exponent is calculated, the Jacobian of the chaotic dynamics is required. The Jacobian of conventional system in this study is shown below:

$$\overrightarrow{J(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} G(x_1(n)) & 0 & g_1 \\ J_1 & J_2 & J_3 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

$$J_1 = h_1 + 2 \cdot h_{11} \cdot x_1(n) + (h_{12} + h_{21}) \cdot x_2(n) + (h_{13} + h_{31}) \cdot x_3(n) + h_{123} \cdot x_2(n) \cdot x_3(n)$$

$$J_2 = h_2 + 2 \cdot h_{22} \cdot x_2(n) + (h_{12} + h_{21}) \cdot x_1(n) + (h_{23} + h_{32}) \cdot x_3(n) + h_{123} \cdot x_1(n) \cdot x_3(n)$$

$$J_3 = h_3 + 2 \cdot h_{33} \cdot x_3(n) + (h_{13} + h_{31}) \cdot x_1(n) + (h_{23} + h_{32}) \cdot x_2(n) + h_{123} \cdot x_1(n) \cdot x_2(n)$$

The Jacobian of proposed system in this study are shown below:

$$\overrightarrow{J(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} J_{11} & J_{12} & J_{13} \\ J_{21} & J_{22} & J_{23} \\ J_{31} & J_{32} & J_{33} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

$$J_{11} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} RBFN(x_1(n), x_2(n), x_3(n)) + g_{123} \cdot x_2(n) \cdot x_3(n)$$

$$J_{12} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} RBFN(x_1(n), x_2(n), x_3(n)) + g_{123} \cdot x_1(n) \cdot x_3(n)$$

$$J_{13} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_3} RBFN(x_1(n), x_2(n), x_3(n)) + g_{123} \cdot x_1(n) \cdot x_2(n)$$

$$J_{21} = h_1 + h_{123} \cdot x_2(n) \cdot x_3(n) + (h_{12} \cdot x_2(n) + (h_{13} + h_{31}) \cdot x_3(n))$$

$$J_{22} = (h_{12} \cdot x_1(n) + (h_{23} + h_{32}) \cdot x_3(n)) + h_{123} \cdot x_1(n) \cdot x_3(n)$$

$$J_{23} = h_3 + h_{123} \cdot x_1(n) \cdot x_2(n) + ((h_{13} + h_{31}) \cdot x_1(n) + (h_{23} + h_{32}) \cdot x_2(n))$$

$$J_{31} = g_1 + ((g_{12} + g_{21}) \cdot x_2(n) + g_{31} \cdot x_3(n))$$

$$J_{32} = 1 + ((g_{12} + g_{21}) \cdot x_1(n) + g_{32} \cdot x_3(n))$$

$$J_{33} = g_3 + (g_{31} \cdot x_1(n) + g_{32} \cdot x_2(n))$$

In the proposed system, each term J_{ij} includes many coefficients and the generated internal state variables $x_1(n)$, $x_2(n)$ and $x_3(n)$, respectively, compared to the conventional

method. Therefore, the Jacobian has the time variant more advanced characteristic, and estimate the private keys by the Lyapunov spectrum analysis based on the time series signal becomes extremely difficult.

Fig. 5 Estimation of the Lyapunov Spectrum (The Conventional System) based on the Time Series Signal. Horizontal Axis Shows the Parameter $h1/1024(Q_{10}Format)$ of the Cipher

Fig. 6 Estimation of the Lyapunov Spectrum (The Proposed System) based on the Time Series Signal. Horizontal Axis Shows the Parameter $h1/1024(Q_{10}Format)$ of the Cipher

The number of sample that is used to estimate the Lyapunov exponent is 10,000. When parameter h_{123} is varied in each method, the results from the evaluation of the Lyapunov exponent shown in Fig. 5, 6. In this evaluation, the parameter is changed in increments of 0. 1 in the range from Q_{10min} to Q_{10max} . As the Fig. 6 shows, the value of the second and third Lyapunov exponent is larger than the result shown in Fig. 5. Furthermore, the decrease of the value has been reduced in the vicinity of the zero point in the first Lyapunov exponent, compared to the conventional method.

